

Separation Axioms in Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces

Ahmed B. AL-Nafee¹, Riad K. Al-Hamido², Florentin Smarandache³

¹ College of Education For Pure sciences Math Dept., Babylon University, Babylon, Iraq, E-mail: Ahm_math_88@yahoo.com

² Faculty of science, Department of mathematics, Al-Baath University, Homs, Syria., E-mail: riadhamido1983@hotmail.com

³ Department of Mathematics, University of New Mexico 705 Gurley Ave. Gallup, NM 87301, USA, Email: smarand@unm.edu

Abstract. The main idea of this research is to define a new neutrosophic crisp points in neutrosophic crisp topological space namely $[NCP_N]$ the concept of neutrosophic crisp limit point was defined using $[NCP_N]$, with some of its properties, the separation axioms $[N-\mathcal{T}_i\text{-space}, i=0,1,2]$ were constructed in neutrosophic crisp topological space using $[NCP_N]$ and examine the relationship between them in details.

Keywords: Neutrosophic crisp topological spaces, neutrosophic crisp limit point, separation axioms.

Introduction

Smarandache [1,2,3] introduced the notions of neutrosophic theory and introduced the neutrosophic components (T, I, F) which represent the membership, indeterminacy, and non membership values respectively, where $]-0,1^+[$ is a non standard unit interval. In [4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20] many scientists presented the concepts of the neutrosophic set theory in their works. Salama et al. [21,22] provided natural foundations to put mathematical treatments for the neutrosophic pervasively phenomena in our real world and for building new branches of neutrosophic mathematics.

Salama et al [23,24] put some basic concepts of the neutrosophic crisp set and their operations, and because of their wide applications and their great flexibility to solve the problem, we used these concepts to define new types of neutrosophic points, that we called neutrosophic crisp points $[NCP_N]$.

Finally, we used these points $[NCP_N]$ to define the concept of neutrosophic crisp limit point, with some of its properties and construct the separation axioms $[N-\mathcal{T}_i\text{-space}, i=0,1,2]$ in neutrosophic crisp topological and examine the relationship between them in details.

Throughout this paper, $(NCTS)$ means a neutrosophic crisp topological space. Also, simply we denote neighborhood by (nhd) .

1 Basic Concepts

1.1 Definition [25]

Let \mathcal{X} be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic crisp set $[NCS \text{ for short}] B$ is an object having the form $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ where B_1, B_2 and B_3 are subsets of \mathcal{X} .

1.2 Definition [25]

The object having the form $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ is called :

1. A neutrosophic crisp set of Type1 $[NCS/Type1]$ if satisfying $B_1 \cap B_2 = \emptyset, B_1 \cap B_3 = \emptyset$ and $B_2 \cap B_3 = \emptyset$.
2. A neutrosophic crisp set of Type2 $[NCS/Type2]$ if satisfying $B_1 \cap B_2 = \emptyset, B_1 \cap B_3 = \emptyset$ and $B_2 \cap B_3 = \emptyset, B_1 \cup B_2 \cup B_3 = \mathcal{X}$.
3. A neutrosophic crisp set of Type3 $[NCS/Type3]$ if satisfying $B_1 \cap B_2 \cap B_3 = \emptyset, B_1 \cup B_2 \cup B_3 = \mathcal{X}$

1.3 Definition [25]

Types of NCSs \emptyset_N & \mathcal{X}_N in \mathcal{X} as follows :

1. \emptyset_N may be defined in many ways as a NCS as follows :
 1. Type1 : $\emptyset_N = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \mathcal{X} \rangle$
 2. Type2 : $\emptyset_N = \langle \emptyset, \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{X} \rangle$
 3. Type3 : $\emptyset_N = \langle \emptyset, \mathcal{X}, \emptyset \rangle$
 4. Type4 : $\emptyset_N = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$
2. \mathcal{X}_N may be defined in many ways as a NCS as follows :
 1. Type1: $\mathcal{X}_N = \langle \mathcal{X}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$

2. Type2: $\mathcal{X}_N = \langle \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{X}, \varphi \rangle$
3. Type3: $\mathcal{X}_N = \langle \mathcal{X}, \varphi, \mathcal{X} \rangle$
4. Type4: $\mathcal{X}_N = \langle \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{X} \rangle$

1.4 Definition [25]

Let \mathcal{X} be a non-empty set and the NCSs C & D in the form $C = \langle C_1, C_2, C_3 \rangle$, $D = \langle D_1, D_2, D_3 \rangle$ then we may consider two possible definitions for subsets $C \subseteq D$, may be defined in two ways :

1. $C \subseteq D \Leftrightarrow C_1 \subseteq D_1, C_2 \subseteq D_2$ and $D_3 \subseteq C_3$
2. $C \subseteq D \Leftrightarrow C_1 \subseteq D_1, D_2 \subseteq C_2$ and $D_3 \subseteq C_3$

1.5 Definition [25]

Let \mathcal{X} be a non-empty set and the NCSs C & D in the form $C = \langle C_1, C_2, C_3 \rangle$, $D = \langle D_1, D_2, D_3 \rangle$ then :

1. $C \cap D$ may be defined in two ways as a NCS as follows :
 - $C \cap D = [C_1 \cap D_1], [C_2 \cup D_2], [C_3 \cup D_3]$
 - $C \cap D = [C_1 \cap D_1], [C_2 \cap D_2], [C_3 \cup D_3]$
2. $C \cup D$ may be defined in two ways as a NCS as follows :
 - $C \cup D = [C_1 \cup D_1], [C_2 \cup D_2], [C_3 \cap D_3]$
 - $C \cup D = [C_1 \cup D_1], [C_2 \cap D_2], [C_3 \cap D_3]$

1.6 Definition [25]

A neutrosophic crisp topology (NCT) on a non-empty set \mathcal{X} is a family \mathcal{T} of neutrosophic crisp subsets in \mathcal{X} satisfying the following axioms :

1. $\emptyset_N, \mathcal{X}_N \in \mathcal{T}$
2. $C \cap D \in \mathcal{T}$, for any $C, D \in \mathcal{T}$
3. The union of any number of sets in \mathcal{T} belongs to \mathcal{T}

The pair $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ is said to be a neutrosophic crisp topological space (NCTS) in \mathcal{X} . Moreover The elements in \mathcal{T} are said to be neutrosophic crisp open sets (NCOS), a neutrosophic crisp set F is closed (NCCS) iff its complement F^c is an open neutrosophic crisp set.

1.7 Definition [25]

Let \mathcal{X} be a non-empty set and the NCS D in the form $D = \langle D_1, D_2, D_3 \rangle$. Then D^c may be defined in three ways as a NCS as follows :

$$D^c = \langle D_1^c, D_2^c, D_3^c \rangle, D^c = \langle D_3, D_2, D_1 \rangle \text{ or } D^c = \langle D_3, D_2^c, D_1 \rangle$$

1.8 Definition [25]

Let $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ be neutrosophic crisp topological space (NCTS). A be neutrosophic crisp set then: The intersection of any neutrosophic crisp closed sets contained, A is called neutrosophic crisp closure of A (NC-Cl(A)) for short).

2 Neutrosophic crisp limit point :

In this section, we will introduce the neutrosophic crisp limit points with some of its properties. This work contains an adjustment for the above-mentioned definitions 1.4 & 1.5, this was necessary to homogeneous suitable results for the upgrade of this research.

2.1 Definition

Let \mathcal{X} be a non-empty set and the NCSs C & D in the form $C = \langle C_1, C_2, C_3 \rangle$, $D = \langle D_1, D_2, D_3 \rangle$ then the additional new ways for the intersection, union and inclusion between C & D are

$$C \cap D = [C_1 \cap D_1], [C_2 \cap D_2], [C_3 \cap D_3]$$

$$C \cup D = [C_1 \cup D_1], [C_2 \cup D_2], [C_3 \cup D_3]$$

$$C \subseteq D \Leftrightarrow C_1 \subseteq D_1, C_2 \subseteq D_2 \text{ and } C_3 \subseteq D_3$$

2.2 Definition

For all x, y, z belonging to a non-empty set \mathcal{X} . Then the neutrosophic crisp points related to x, y, z are defined as follows :

- $x_{N_1} = \langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$, is called a neutrosophic crisp point (NCP_{N_1}) in \mathcal{X} .
- $y_{N_2} = \langle \emptyset, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle$, is called a neutrosophic crisp point (NCP_{N_2}) in \mathcal{X} .
- $z_{N_3} = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{z\} \rangle$, is called a neutrosophic crisp point (NCP_{N_3}) in \mathcal{X} .

The set of all neutrosophic crisp points ($NCP_{N_1}, NCP_{N_2}, NCP_{N_3}$) is denoted by NCP_N .

2.3 Definition

Let \mathcal{X} be to a non-empty set and $x, y, z \in \mathcal{X}$. Then the neutrosophic crisp point:

- x_{N_1} is belonging to the neutrosophic crisp set $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, denoted by $x_{N_1} \in B$, if $x \in B_1$, wherein x_{N_1} does not belong to the neutrosophic crisp set B denoted by $x_{N_1} \notin B$, if $x \notin B_1$.
- y_{N_2} is belonging to the neutrosophic crisp set $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, denoted by $y_{N_2} \in B$, if $y \in B_2$. In contrast y_{N_2} does not belong to the neutrosophic crisp set B , denoted by $y_{N_2} \notin B$, if $y \notin B_2$.
- z_{N_3} is belonging to the neutrosophic crisp set $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$, denoted by $z_{N_3} \in B$, if $z \in B_3$. In contrast z_{N_3} does not belong to the neutrosophic crisp set B , denoted by $z_{N_3} \notin B$, if $z \notin B_3$.

2.4 Remark

If $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ is a NCS in a non-empty set \mathcal{X} then :

$B \setminus x_{N_1} = \langle B_1 \setminus \{x\}, B_2, B_3 \rangle$. $B \setminus x_{N_1}$ means that the component B doesn't contain x_{N_1} .

$B \setminus y_{N_2} = \langle B_1, B_2 \setminus \{y\}, B_3 \rangle$. $B \setminus y_{N_2}$ means that the component B doesn't contain y_{N_2} .

$B \setminus z_{N_3} = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \setminus \{z\} \rangle$. $B \setminus z_{N_3}$ means that the component B doesn't contain z_{N_3} .

2.5 Example

If $B = \langle \{a, b\}, \{c, b\}, \{c, a\} \rangle$ is an NCS in $\mathcal{X} = \{a, b, c\}$, then:

$B \setminus a_{N_1} = \langle \{b\}, \{c, b\}, \{c, a\} \rangle$

$B \setminus b_{N_2} = \langle \{a, b\}, \{c\}, \{c, a\} \rangle$

$B \setminus c_{N_3} = \langle \{a, b\}, \{c, b\}, \{b\} \rangle$

2.6 Remark

If $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ is a NCS in a non-empty set \mathcal{X} then :

$$B = (U\{x_{N_1} : x_{N_1} \in B\}) \cup (U\{y_{N_2} : y_{N_2} \in B\}) \cup (\cap\{z_{N_3} : z_{N_3} \in B\})$$

$$= (U\{\langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}\}) \cup (U\{\langle \emptyset, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle : y \in \mathcal{X}\}) \cup (\cap\{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{z\} \rangle : z \in \mathcal{X}\})$$

or

$$B = (U\{x_{N_1} : x_{N_1} \in B\}) \cup (U\{y_{N_2} : y_{N_2} \in B\}) \cup (U\{z_{N_3} : z_{N_3} \in B\})$$

$$= (U\{\langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle : x \in \mathcal{X}\}) \cup (U\{\langle \emptyset, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle : y \in \mathcal{X}\}) \cup (U\{\langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{z\} \rangle : z \in \mathcal{X}\}).$$

2.7 Definition

Let $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ be NCTS, $P \in NCP_N$ in \mathcal{X} , a neutrosophic crisp set $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle \in \mathcal{T}$ is called neutrosophic crisp open nhd of P in $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ if $P \in B$.

2.8 Definition

Let $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ be NCTS, $P \in NCP_N$ in \mathcal{X} , a neutrosophic crisp set $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle \in \mathcal{T}$ is called neutrosophic crisp nhd of P in $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$, if there is neutrosophic crisp open set $A = \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle$ containing P such that $A \subseteq B$.

2.9 Note

Every neutrosophic crisp open nhd of any point $P \in NCP_N$ in \mathcal{X} is neutrosophic crisp nhd of P , but in general the inverse is not true, the following example illustrates this fact.

2.10 Example

If $\mathcal{X} = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, A, B, C\}$,

$A = \langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$, $B = \langle \{y\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$, $G = \langle \{x, y\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$

If we take $U = \langle \{x, y\}, \{z\}, \emptyset \rangle$.

Then $G = \langle \{x, y\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$ is an open set containing $P = x_{N_1} = \langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$ and $G \subseteq U$. That is U is a neutrosophic crisp nhd of P in $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$, while it is not a neutrosophic crisp open nhd of P .

2.11 Definition

Let $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ be NCTS and $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ be NCS of \mathcal{X} . A neutrosophic crisp point $P \in NCP_N$ in \mathcal{X} is called a neutrosophic crisp limit point of $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ iff every neutrosophic crisp open set containing P must contains at least one neutrosophic crisp point of B different from P . It is easy to say that the point P is not neutrosophic crisp limit point of B if there is a neutrosophic crisp open set G of P and $B \cap (G \setminus P) = \emptyset_N$.

2.12 Definition

The set of all neutrosophic crisp limit points of a neutrosophic crisp set B is called neutrosophic crisp derived set of B , denoted by $NCD(B)$.

2.13 Example

If $\mathcal{X} = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, A, B, C\}$, $A = \langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$, $B = \langle \{y\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$, $G = \langle \{x, y\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$. If we take $D = \langle \{x, y\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$, Then $P = Z_{N_1} = \langle \{Z\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle$ is the only neutrosophic crisp limit point of D . i.e. $NCD(D) = \{Z_{N_1}\}$

2.14 Remarks

- Let B be any neutrosophic crisp set of \mathcal{X} , If $P = \langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle \in \mathcal{T}$ in any NCT space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$, then $P \in NCD(B)$.
- Let B be any neutrosophic crisp set of \mathcal{X} , the following facts is true:
 $NCD(B) \not\subseteq B$, $B \not\subseteq NCD(B)$, and sometimes $NCD(B) \cap B = \emptyset_N$ or $NCD(B) \cap B \neq \emptyset_N$.
- In any NCT space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$, we have $NCD(\emptyset) = \emptyset_N$.

2.15 Theorem

Let $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ be NCTS and $B = \langle B_1, B_2, B_3 \rangle$ be a neutrosophic crisp set of \mathcal{X} , then B is neutrosophic crisp closed set (NCCS for short) iff $NCD(B) \subseteq B$

Proof

Let B be NCCS, then $(\mathcal{X} \setminus B)$ is neutrosophic crisp open set (NCOS for short) this implies that for each neutrosophic crisp point $P \in NCP_N$ in $(\mathcal{X} \setminus B)$, $P \notin B$, there is a neutrosophic crisp open set G of P and $G \subseteq (\mathcal{X} \setminus B)$.

Since $B \cap (\mathcal{X} \setminus B) = \emptyset_N$, then P is not neutrosophic crisp limit point of B , thus $G \cap B = \emptyset_N$, which implies that $P \notin NCD(B)$. Hence $NCD(B) \subseteq B$

Conversely, assume that $P \notin NCD(B)$, implies that P is not neutrosophic crisp limit point of B , hence, there is a neutrosophic crisp open set G of P and $G \cap B = \emptyset_N$ which means that $G \subseteq (\mathcal{X} \setminus B)$ and since $(\mathcal{X} \setminus B)$ is a neutrosophic crisp open set. Hence B is neutrosophic crisp closed set.

2.16 Theorem

Let $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ be NCTS, B, G be a neutrosophic crisp sets of \mathcal{X} , then the following properties hold:

- (1) $NCD(\emptyset_N) = \emptyset_N$
- (2) If $B \subseteq G$, then $NCD(B) \subseteq NCD(G)$
- (3) $NCD(B \cap G) \subseteq NCD(B) \cap NCD(G)$
- (4) $NCD(B \cup G) = NCD(B) \cup NCD(G)$

Proof (1) the proof is, directly.

Proof (2)

Assume that $NCD(B)$ be a neutrosophic crisp set containing a neutrosophic crisp point $P \in NCP_N$, then by definition 2.11, for each neutrosophic crisp open set V of P , we have $B \cap V \setminus P \neq \emptyset_N$, but $B \subseteq G$, hence $G \cap V \setminus P \neq \emptyset_N$, this means that $P \in NCD(G)$. Hence, $NCD(B) \subseteq NCD(G)$

Proof (3)

Since $B \cap G \subseteq B$, then by (2) $NCD(B \cap G) \subseteq NCD(B)$ (1)

$B \cap G \subseteq G$, implies $NCD(B \cap G) \subseteq NCD(G)$ (2)

From (1) & (2) $NCD(B \cap G) \subseteq NCD(B) \cap NCD(G)$

Proof (4)

Let $P \in NCP_N$ such that $P \notin NCD(B) \cup NCD(G)$, then either $P \notin NCD(B)$ and $P \notin NCD(G)$, then there is a neutrosophic crisp open set K of P and $B \cap K \setminus P = \emptyset_N$ and $G \cap K \setminus P = \emptyset_N$, this implies that $(B \cup G) \cap K \setminus P = \emptyset_N$, i.e $P \notin NCD(B \cup G)$, hence $NCD(B \cup G) \subseteq NCD(B) \cup NCD(G)$ (3)

Conversely, since $B \subseteq B \cup G, G \subseteq B \cup G$, then by property (2) $NCD(B) \subseteq NCD(B \cup G)$ and $NCD(G) \subseteq NCD(B \cup G)$, thus $NCD(B \cup G) \supseteq NCD(B) \cup NCD(G)$ (4)

from (3) and (4) we have $NCD(B \cup G) = NCD(B) \cup NCD(G)$.

2.17 Remark

In general, the inverse of property 2 & 3 in Th.(2.16) is not true. The following examples act as an evidence to this claim.

2.18 Example

If $\mathcal{X} = \{x, y, z\}, \mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, B\}, B = \langle \emptyset, \{x\}, \emptyset \rangle$. If we take $A = \langle \emptyset, \{x\}, \emptyset \rangle, G = \langle \emptyset, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle$. Notes that; $NCD(A) = \langle \emptyset, \{y, z\}, \emptyset \rangle, NCD(G) = \langle \emptyset, \{y, z\}, \emptyset \rangle$ and $NCD(A) \subseteq NCD(G)$, but $A \not\subseteq G$.

2.19 Example

If $\mathcal{X} = \{x, y, z\}, \mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, B\}, B = \langle \emptyset, \{x\}, \emptyset \rangle$. If we take $A = \langle \emptyset, \{x\}, \emptyset \rangle, G = \langle \emptyset, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle$. Notes that; $NCD(B \cap G) \not\supseteq NCD(B) \cap NCD(G)$.

2.20 Theorem

For any neutrosophic crisp set B over the universe \mathcal{X} , then $NC-CI(B) = B \cup NCD(B)$

Proof

Let us first prove that $B \cup NCD(B)$ is a neutrosophic crisp closed set that is

$\mathcal{X}_N \setminus (B \cup NCD(B)) = (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus B) \cap (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus NCD(B))$ is a neutrosophic crisp open set .

Now for a neutrosophic crisp point $P \in (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus (B \cup NCD(B))) \cap (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus NCD(B))$, then $P \in (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus (B))$ and $P \in \mathcal{X}_N \setminus NCD(B)$, thus $P \notin B$ and $P \notin NCD(B)$. So by definition 2.12, there is a neutrosophic crisp set R of P s.t $R \cap B = \emptyset_N$, hence $R \subseteq \mathcal{X}_N \setminus B$.

Now for each $P_1 \in R$, then $P_1 \notin NCD(B)$, then $R \cap NCD(B) = \emptyset_N$, this implies that $R \subseteq \mathcal{X}_N \setminus NCD(B)$ [i.e $R \subseteq (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus B) \cap (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus NCD(B))$]. Thus $(\mathcal{X}_N \setminus B) \cap (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus NCD(B))$ is a neutrosophic crisp nhd of all its elements and hence $(\mathcal{X}_N \setminus B) \cap (\mathcal{X}_N \setminus NCD(B))$ is a neutrosophic crisp open set and thus $B \cup NCD(B)$ is a neutrosophic crisp closed set containing B , therefore $NC-CI(B) \subseteq B \cup NCD(B)$. Since $NC-CI(B)$ is a neutrosophic crisp closed set (see definition 2.12) and $NC-CI(B)$ contains all its neutrosophic crisp limits points .Thus $NCD(B) \subseteq NC-CI(B)$ and $B \subseteq NC-CI(B)$, hence $NC-CI(B) = B \cup NCD(B)$.

3 Separation Axioms In a neutrosophic Crisp Topological Space

3.1 Definition

A neutrosophic crisp topological space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ is called:

- N_1 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space if $\forall x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open set G in \mathcal{X} containing one of them but not the other.
- N_2 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open set G in \mathcal{X} containing one of them but not the other .
- N_3 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open set G in \mathcal{X} containing one of them but not the other .
- N_1 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space if $\forall x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open sets G_1, G_2 in \mathcal{X} such that $x_{N_1} \in G_1, y_{N_1} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin G_2, y_{N_1} \in G_2$
- N_2 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open sets G_1, G_2 in \mathcal{X} such that $x_{N_2} \in G_1, y_{N_2} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin G_2, y_{N_2} \in G_2$
- N_3 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open sets G_1, G_2 in \mathcal{X} such that $x_{N_3} \in G_1, y_{N_3} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin G_2, y_{N_3} \in G_2$
- N_1 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space if $\forall x_{N_1} \neq y_{N_1} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open sets G_1, G_2 in \mathcal{X} such that $x_{N_1} \in G_1, y_{N_1} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_1} \notin G_2, y_{N_1} \in G_2$ with $G_1 \cap G_2 = \emptyset$.
- N_2 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space if $\forall x_{N_2} \neq y_{N_2} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open sets G_1, G_2 in \mathcal{X} such that $x_{N_2} \in G_1, y_{N_2} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_2} \notin G_2, y_{N_2} \in G_2$ with $G_1 \cap G_2 = \emptyset$.

- N_3 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space if $\forall x_{N_3} \neq y_{N_3} \in \mathcal{X} \exists$ a neutrosophic crisp open sets G_1, G_2 in \mathcal{X} such that $x_{N_3} \in G_1, y_{N_3} \notin G_1$ and $x_{N_3} \notin G_2, y_{N_3} \in G_2$ with $G_1 \cap G_2 = \emptyset$.

3.2 Definition

A neutrosophic crisp topological space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ is called:

- N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space if $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ is N_1 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space, N_2 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space and N_3 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space
- N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space if $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ is N_1 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space, N_2 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space and N_3 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space
- N - \mathcal{T}_2 -space if $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ is N_1 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space, N_2 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space and N_3 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space

3.3 Remark

For a neutrosophic crisp topological space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$

- Every N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space is N_1 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space
- Every N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space is N_2 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space
- Every N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space is N_3 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space

Proof the proof is directly from definition 3.2.

The inverse of remark 3.3 is not true, the following example explain this state.

3.4 Example

If $\mathcal{X} = \{x, y\}, \mathcal{T}_1 = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, A\}, \mathcal{T}_2 = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, B\}, \mathcal{T}_3 = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, G\}, A = \langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle, B = \langle \emptyset, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle, G = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{x\} \rangle$, Then $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T}_1)$ is N_1 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space but it is not N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space, $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T}_2)$ is N_2 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space but it is not N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space, $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T}_3)$ is N_3 - \mathcal{T}_0 -space but it is not N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space.

3.5 Remark

For a neutrosophic crisp topological space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$

- Every N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space is N_1 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space
- Every N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space is N_2 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space
- Every N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space is N_3 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space

Proof the proof is directly from definition 3.2.

The inverse of remark (3.5) is not true as it is shown in the following example,

3.6 Example

If $\mathcal{X} = \{x, y\}, \mathcal{T}_1 = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, A, B\}, \mathcal{T}_2 = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, G, F\}, A = \langle \{x\}, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle, B = \langle \{y\}, \{x\}, \emptyset \rangle, G = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{x\} \rangle, F = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{y\} \rangle$, Then $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T}_1)$ is N_1 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space but it is not N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space. $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T}_1)$ is N_2 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space but it is not N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space. $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T}_2)$ is N_3 - \mathcal{T}_1 -space but it is not N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space

3.7 Remark

For a neutrosophic crisp topological space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$

- Every N - \mathcal{T}_2 -space is N_1 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space
- Every N - \mathcal{T}_2 -space is N_2 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space
- Every N - \mathcal{T}_2 -space is N_3 - \mathcal{T}_2 -space

Proof the proof is directly from definition 3.2.

The inverse of remark (3.7) is not true as it is shown in the example (3.6).

3.8 Remark

For a neutrosophic crisp topological space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$

- Every N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space is N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space
- Every N - \mathcal{T}_2 -space is N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space

Proof the proof is directly.

The inverse of remark (3.8) is not true as it is shown in the following example :

3.9 Example

If $\mathcal{X} = \{x, y\}, \mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{X}_N, \emptyset_N, A, B, G\}$

$A = \langle \{x\}, \emptyset, \emptyset \rangle, B = \langle \emptyset, \{y\}, \emptyset \rangle, G = \langle \emptyset, \emptyset, \{x\} \rangle,$

Then $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{T})$ is N - \mathcal{T}_0 -space but not N - \mathcal{T}_1 -space

Conclusion

- We defined a new neutrosophic crisp points in neutrosophic crisp topological space
- We introduced the concept of neutrosophic crisp limit point, with some of its properties
- We constructed the separation axioms $[N-\mathcal{T}_i\text{-space}, i=0,1,2]$ in neutrosophic crisp topological and examine the relationship between them in details.

Acknowledgment

Deep thanks and kindly gratefully goes for Dr.Huda E.Khalid and Eng.Ahmed K.Essa/ the advisor of neutrosophic science international association NSIA/ Iraqi branch, for their advice, worthy comments to improve this work, they revised this work scientifically, and being in touch with us to upgrade our article to get merit for publishing in the NSS journal.

References

- [1] F. Smarandache. Neutrosophy and Neutrosophic Logic, First International Conference on Neutrosophy, Neuro sophic Logic, Set, Probability, and Statistics, University of New Mexico, NM 87301, USA (2002)
- [2] F. Smarandache. A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability, American Re- search Press, Rehoboth, NM, (1999)
- [3] F. Smarandache. An introduction to the Neutrosophy probability applied in Quantum Physics, International Conference on introduction Neutrosophic Physics, Neutrosophic Logic, Set, Probability, and Statistics, University of New Mexico, Gallup, NM 87301, USA2-4 December (2011)
- [4] A. A. Salama. Basic Structure of Some Classes of Neutrosophic Crisp Nearly Open Sets and Possible Application to GIS Topology. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol.(7),(2015),18-22.
- [5] W. Al-Omeri, Neutrosophic crisp Sets via Neutrosophic crisp Topological Spaces NCTS, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol.13, 2016, pp.96-104
- [6] A. A. Salama and F. Smarandache. Filters via Neutrosophic Crisp Sets, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 1, Issue 1, (2013), 34-38.
- [7] A. A. Salama and H. Elagamy. Neutrosophic Filters. International Journal of Computer Science Engineering and Information Technology Research (IJCSSEITR), Vol.3, Issue 1, (2013), 307-312.
- [8] A. A. Salama and S.A. Alblowi. Intuitionistic Fuzzy Ideals Topological Spaces. Advances in Fuzzy Mathematics, Vol.(7), Issue 1, (2012), 51- 60
- [9] A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi. Neutrosophic set and neutrosophic topological space. ISORJ, Mathematics, Vol. (3), Issue 4, (2012), 31-35
- [10] D. Sarker. Fuzzy ideal theory, Fuzzy local function and generated fuzzy topology. Fuzzy Sets and Systems 87, (1997), 117-123
- [11] H. E. Khalid, "An Original Notion to Find Maximal Solution in the Fuzzy Neutrosophic Relation Equations (FNRE) with Geometric Programming (GP)",Neutrosophic Sets and Systems,vol.7,2015,pp.3-7.
- [12] I. Hanafy, A. A. Salama and K. Mahfouz. Correlation of neutrosophic data, International Refereed Journal of Engineering and Science (IRJES), Vol.(1), Issue 2 , (2012), 39-43.
- [13] S. A. Alblowi, A. A. Salama and Mohamed Eisa. New concepts of neutrosophic sets. International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Applications Research (IJMCAR), Vol. (4), Issue 1, (2014), 59-66.
- [14] A. A. Salama, I.M.Hanafy, Hewayda Elghawalby, M.S.Dabash. Neutrosophic Crisp Closed Region and Neutrosophic Crisp Continuous Functions. In F. Smarandache, & S. Pramanik (Eds.), New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications (pp. 403-412). Brussels: Pons Editions (2016).
- [15] M. Abdel-Basset, M. Saleh, A. Gamal, F.Smarandache An approach of TOPSIS technique for developing supplier selection with group decision making under type-2 neutrosophic number, Applied Soft Computing, Volume 77, April 2019, Pages 438-452
- [16] M. Abdel-Basset, G. Manogaran, A. Gamal, F. Smarandach, A Group Decision Making Framework Based on Neutrosophic TOPSIS Approach for Smart Medical Device Selection. J. Medical Systems 43(2): (2019), 38:1-38:13 .
- [17] M. Abdel Basset, V. Chang, A. Gamal, F. Smarandache, Anintegrated neutrosophic ANP and VIKOR method for achieving sustainable supplier selection: A case study in importing field. Computers in Industry, 106: (2019), 94-110 .
- [18] M. Parimala, M. Karthika, S. Jafari , F. Smarandache 4, R.Udhayakumar5_. Neutrosophic Nano ideal topological structure, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 24, (2019), 70-76
- [19] S. Saranya and M.Vigneshwaran., Neutrosophic b_g -Closed Sets, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 24, (2019), 90-99
- [20] A. B. AL-Nafee, R. D. Ali. On Idea of Controlling Soft Gem-Set in Soft Topological Space, Jour of Adv Research in Dynamical & Control Systems, Vol. 10, 13-Special Issue, (2018) , 606-615

- <http://jardcs.org/backissues/abstract.php?archiveid=6022>
- [21] A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi. Generalized Neutrosophic Set and Generalized Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, Journal computer Sci. Engineering, Vol. (2) , Issue 7, (2012), 29-32.
- [22] A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi. Intuitionistic Fuzzy Ideals Topological Spaces, Advances in Fuzzy Mathematics, Vol.(7), Issue 1, (2012), 51- 60
- [23] I. M. Hanafy, A. A. Salama and K.M. Mahfouz. Neutrosophic crisp events and its probability. International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Applications Research (IJMCAR), Vol.(3), Issue 1, (2013), 171-178.
- [24] A. A. Salama. Neutrosophic Crisp Points and Neutrosophic Crisp Ideals. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol.1, Issue 1, (2013), 50-54.
- [25] A. A. Salama, F. Smarandache and Valeri Kroumov. Neutrosophic Crisp Sets and Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. (2), (2014), 25-30.
- [26] A. B. Al-Nafee, L.A. Al-Swidi,. "Separation Axioms Using Soft Turing Point of a Soft Ideal in Soft Topological Space". Journal of New Theory (2018): 29-37
- [27] A. AL-Nafee, "On *Soft Turing Point with Separation Axioms", *JUBPAS*, vol. 26, no. 7, 2018, pp. 200 – 209 .

Received: December 11, 2018. Accepted: January 14, 2019